

Appendix

“Believing in Credibility Measures: Reviewing Credibility Measures in Media Research”

Literature search and Codebook

The subsequent table summarizes the keywords used for the literature search. We opted for a broad search strategy since credibility is related to other concepts such as “trust” and often conflated with these concepts. We therefore also included search terms related to these related concepts (e.g., “trust”). Manually filtering the results guaranteed that we could eliminate those contributions from the sample that were clearly talking about distinct concepts from credibility, while keeping those that despite using a different wording were talking about credibility.

Table A1. Search Terms

Database	Search term
<i>EBSCOhost</i>	TI (Credibility OR credibl* OR trust OR persuas* OR attitude) AND AB (credibility OR credibl* OR trust) AND AB (communication OR media OR news OR information)
<i>Web of Science</i>	TI=(credibility OR credibl* OR trust OR persuas* OR attitude) AND TS=(credibility OR credibl* OR trust) AND TS=(communication OR media OR news OR information)

Note: “TI” stands for title and the command returns results whose titles contain any one of the terms in the parentheses. The option “OR” allows us to search for multiple terms at the same time and returns either one or both keywords in the results. The star following a keyword allows us to broaden the search by finding words that start with the same letters. The “AND” command returns results that simultaneously satisfy the first the second, and the third conditions of the search. In the first particular case, results that contain the keywords, or variations thereof, in both their titles and their abstracts. Finally, “AB” stands for abstract. The Web of Science website does not provide the option of looking for keywords only in articles’ abstracts. The option “TS” looks for the keywords in articles’ titles, abstracts, and keywords.

Table A2. Codebook

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
<i>id_scale</i>	Scale identification	Assigns each scale a unique identification number ranging from 1 to N_scale	-
<i>id_article</i>	Article identification	Assigns each article a unique identification number ranging from 1 to N_article	-
<i>author</i>	Names of all authors	Lists the article's author(s)	-
<i>title</i>	Article title	Records the article's full title	-
<i>year</i>	Article's publication year	Records the article's year of publication	
<i>abstract</i>	Article abstract	Provides the article's abstract	
<i>journal</i>	Article journal	Records the full name of the journal the article appears in	
<i>pages</i>	Article pages	Records the exact pages the article starts and ends on in the journal issue where it was published	-
<i>jgnr</i>	Article volume and issue	Records the journal volume and issue where the article appeared	e.g., 13(2)
<i>keywords</i>	Article keywords	Lists the article's keywords	-
<i>source</i>	Article source	Describes how the article was identified: 0=database search, 1=snowball system	-
<i>coded</i>	Article is coded	Reports whether the article is coded or not. The article is only coded if it meets the four criteria set for the first article selection: 0=not coded, 1=coded Note about coding: If different articles from the same authors use the same database (i.e., same sample) and the same measurement, the measurement is only coded once since, strictly speaking, the same	

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		observation would otherwise appear twice in the dataset. However, if the same measurement is applied to different samples in the same article, each scale that is applied to a distinct sample should be coded separately.	
<i>construct</i>	Measured construct's original name	Records the measured construct's original name	
<i>construct_cat</i>	Attribution of the construct to source, media, or message	<p>Attributes each construct to either source, message or medium: (.)=unclear, 1=source, 2=media, 3=message.</p> <p>Note about coding:</p> <p>Sometimes it is difficult to distinguish between source and media, especially in the context of online media. Moreover, not all articles explicitly refer to source or media/medium or use the two words interchangeably. The variable is coded as "media" when author(s) are interested in the credibility of media types (e.g., the Internet) or subsystems of media types (e.g., blogs in general, online news in general, broadsheet vs. tabloid). It is coded as "source" if the author(s) are interested in the credibility of specific media products (e.g., a specific website), media organizations (e.g., the BBC), actors (e.g., a president in an interview), or presenters (e.g., the anchor of a TV show). Finally, "message" obtains if the author(s) are</p>	See the note on the left

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		interested in the credibility of editorial units (e.g., a specific news item, an article). ¹	
<i>source_details1</i>	Details if construct_cat=1: known or unknown source	Codes if the source is known or unknown: 0=unknown, 1=known, 2=both (e.g., a known and an unknown source)	e.g., unknown=a journalist, known=Donald Trump
<i>source_details2</i>	Details if construct_cat=1: individual or collective source	Codes if the source is an individual or a collective actor: 0=individual, 1=collective, 2=both Note about coding: If the article's author(s) refers to the source as a group of people (e.g., government officials), this variable obtains a value of 1 (collective).	e.g., collective=an organization/institution/website (several authors); individual=a person/journalist (single author)
<i>source_details3</i>	Details if construct_cat=1: expert or non-expert	Codes if the source is an expert or not (i.e., authors have to refer to sources as professionals, experts, or scientists): 0=no expert, 1=expert, 2=both	e.g., expert=a scientist; no expert=a friend
<i>message_details1</i>	Details if construct_cat=3: type of message	Codes the type of the message: 1=text (incl. illustration), 2=audio, 3=visual (moving), 4=various	e.g., text=news articles , audio=radio emission/speech, visual=TV clip
<i>message_details2</i>	Details if construct_cat=3: message conveys expertise or not	Codes if the message conveys expertise: 0=no expertise, 1=expertise, 2=both Note about coding: The variable obtains a value of 2 if only certain aspects of the message convey expertise (e.g., a message from a doctor vs. a message from a layperson)	e.g., expertise=study/statement from expert

¹ The categories of media type, subsystem of media type, etc., are borrowed from Schweiger (2000).

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
<i>media_details</i>	Details if construct_cat=2: message comes from an expert medium or not	Codes if the message comes from an expert medium or not: 0=no expert medium, 1=expert medium, 2=both (e.g., an expert and a non-expert medium)	e.g., expert=science magazine
<i>media_newspaper</i>	Details if construct_cat=2: medium is a newspaper/magazine or not	0=not a newspaper/magazine, 1=newspaper/magazine	e.g., NZZ
<i>media_internet</i>	Details if construct_cat=2: medium is part of the Internet or not	0=not Internet 1=Internet Note about coding: Newspaper websites are coded as 1 (Internet)	e.g., blog, website, news sites (NBC, MSNBC, etc.)
<i>media_tv</i>	Details if construct_cat=2: medium is tv or not	0=not tv, 1=tv	-
<i>media_radio</i>	Details if construct_cat=2: medium is radio or not	0=not radio, 1=radio	-
<i>media_others</i>	Details if construct_cat=2: medium is other than the media mentioned above	0=no others, 1=others	e.g., interpersonal
<i>comm_context</i>	Communication context	1=online,2=offline (newspaper, magazines), 3=TV, 4=radio, 5=other/various	e.g., online=website credibility
<i>def_dummy</i>	Definition available	Codes if the article's theoretical part provides a definition of credibility: 0=no/not in theoretical part, 1=yes	

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		<p>Note about coding: “Yes” only obtains if 1) the author(s) explicitly states that the provided definition is the one applied in the article (e.g., “In this study, credibility is understood as...”) and 2) the author(s) refers to how credibility is generally understood in the literature (e.g., “Perceived source credibility is typically understood as the believability or trustworthiness of information and/or its source.”). If the author(s) just provides an overview of other scholars’ definitions, this variable is coded as “no.”</p>	
<i>def_literal</i>	Original definition if def_dummy=1	Records credibility’s original definition. All relevant parts of the definition are captured.	e.g., “This study specifically tests the credibility of a news article, and defines it as the public perception of news story quality.” (Pjesivac & Rui, 2014, p. 646)
<i>def_dim</i>	Dimensions of definition	<p>Codes if the author(s) has a unidimensional or a multidimensional understanding of the construct: 0=unidimensional, 1=multidimensional</p> <p>Note about the coding: Multidimensionality is recorded only if the construct of source, message, or medium credibility is understood as consisting of different but related latent variables (e.g., expertise and trustworthiness) that are themselves measured with specific indicators. Our definition does not consider cases in which authors refer to a construct as multidimensional but measure these “dimensions” with a single item. Cases that do not analyze the different dimensions individually</p>	e.g., “Using past studies as a guide (...), credibility was measured as a multidimensional construct.” (Johnson et al., 2007, p. 107)

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		are not considered multidimensional either (for example, see Liu and Huang (2005)).	
<i>dim_names</i>	Names of dimensions if def_dim=1	Records the dimensions' original names and lists the items for each dimension in brackets. Note about coding: If no items are reported or assigned to a particular dimension, the code reads "dimension (items not reported)".	
<i>iv</i>	List of independent variables	Lists the main independent variables of the study at hand. Does not list control variables/covariates.	e.g., racial prejudice, attitude
<i>measure_origin</i>	Measurement origin	Defines the origin of the used measurement: 1=own, 2=adapted replication, 3=replication Note about coding: - 1=no references given/various scales are combined/own items are developed/many items or whole dimensions are replaced or left out/major modification in question wording (code if more or equal to 1/3 of the total number of items was changed/adapted); also if there is no reference to other measurements - 2=minor modifications in question wording; reliance on key scale but exchange of single items (less than 1/3 of the total number of items was changed/adapted) - 3=no changes to the scale at all, except for translation (see below) If the same authors repeatedly use the same scale for the same construct, but always refer to authors other than themselves when they speak	

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		about the scale's origin, only the earliest article is coded as 1; subsequent articles are coded as 3 since they use a replication of the same scale. If one article uses the same scale on two or more different samples, only the first scale is coded as 1, 2, or 3; the remaining times the scale is applied to other samples in the article is coded as 3 (replication).	
<i>measure_transl</i>	Coded if measure_origin=2 or measure_origin=3: measurement translation	Codes if the author(s) translated the measurement or not, but only in the case of (adapted) replications: (.)=not reported/unclear, 0=no, 1=yes Note about coding: If the study uses a scale that was developed in a specific language (e.g., English), we assume that the scale has been translated into the main language of the country in which the study was conducted, if the article does not state otherwise (e.g., German if the study was conducted in Germany).	
<i>measure_ref</i>	Measurement references	Records the references provided for the measurement (see the example on the right for a short reference); we code (.) if the article provides no references to the used measurement Note about coding: See remarks for measure_origin	e.g., Gaziano and McGrath (1986)
<i>measure_type</i>	Measurement type	Records the type of the measurement: (.)=not reported, 1=semantic differential scale, 2=scale (e.g., credibility index, subscales of credibility),	e.g., 2="Respondents were asked how believable, fair, accurate, and in depth they judge blogs, online and traditionally delivered newspapers (...),

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		3= statement(s)/question(s) (not additive), 4=other Note about coding: By 'scale' we understand an "(...) inter-related set of items (...)" (Carifio & Perla, 2007, p. 112). That is, we only code a measurement as a scale if it is used in the form of an index or a subscale.	using a five-point scale, with 1 indicating 'not at all' and 5 indicating 'very'. The four measures were then combined into a credibility index." (Johnson et al., 2007, p. 107)
<i>measure_language</i>	Measurement's original language	Codes the original language in which the measurement was developed: (.)=not reported, 1=German, 2=English, 3=other Note about coding: If cntry (see below) is provided, code for the main language of the provided country (e.g., English, if cntry=USA)	
<i>cntry</i>	Country of the study	Codes the country in which the study was conducted. Provides the full name of the country in English.	
<i>measure_length</i>	Number of items	Codes the number of items used to measure credibility and uses (.) if the number is not reported.	
<i>response_format</i>	Answer categories/points on response scale	Codes the number of answer categories or points on the response scale. Codes (.) if the number is not reported	e.g., do not agree, rather agree, agree=3
<i>item_XX</i>	Items used to measure	Enters a variable for each used item. Records the variable "item_XX" and replaces XX with the name of the item: 0=not used, 1=used, (.)=not reported. Sorts these variables alphabetically into the SPSS-File. Note about coding:	e.g., item_credible; item_actsonbehalfofX e.g., semantic differential scale: "credible – incredible" (=item_credible)

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		<p>If questions or statements are used as measures, we use the relevant parts of the statements (see example). We code items that are similar in meaning but formulated slightly differently (e.g., “can be trusted” and “trustworthy” → item_trustworthy) in the same way. Situations in which the coders were not certain whether the items were similar enough were coded separately.</p> <p>If a semantic differential scale was used, we noted the positively framed attribute as the item’s name.</p>	
<i>sample_size</i>	Sample size	<p>Reports the size of the sample</p> <p>Note about coding: If more than one sample is used, we report the mean of all used samples.</p>	
<i>sample_type</i>	Sample type	<p>Codes the sample type used in the study: (.)=not reported, 1=student, 2=citizens (commercial), 3=citizens (non-commercial), 4=citizens (not random), 5=politicians (elites), 6=professionals, 7=other, 8=different samples/sampling modes</p>	<p>e.g., 2=survey with Amazon Mechanical Turk, 3=survey using population registers, 4=survey posted on a website, 5=politicians, 6=journalists</p>
<i>method</i>	Method used	<p>Records the method used to collect the data: 1=survey, 2=survey with an experiment, 3=experiment, 4=diverse methods (e.g., scale development), 5=other</p> <p>Note about coding: We only code studies that took place in a laboratory setting as experiments.</p>	<p>3=“participants visited a laboratory, viewed a news story, and answered some questions” (Tewksbury et al., 2011, p. 335)</p>

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
<i>valid_test</i>	Validity tests	Codes whether the study conducted validity tests for convergent and/or discriminant validity or factor analysis: 0=no/not reported, 1=yes	1="For a measure to possess good construct validity, it has to be statistically related to other constructs that are logically similar (convergent validity), without being identical to those other constructs (discriminant validity). We compared our credibility measure with other related constructs, including liking and newsworthiness." (Appelman & Sundar, 2016, p. 72)
<i>pretest</i>	Measurement pretest	Codes whether the measurement was pretested in cases that used an adapted scale or adopted a new scale: 0=no/not reported, 1=yes Note about coding: The variable only obtains a value of 1 if the pretest was intended to validate the measurement of credibility. Cases in which the pretest was made for an experiment or for a survey in general were not coded as 1.	
<i>reli_alpha</i>	Cronbach's alpha	Records the Cronbach alpha measurement or (.)=not reported Note about coding: If more than one Cronbach alpha is reported but the author(s) only refers to one as the central dependent variable, we only code the Cronbach alpha for the construct. If more than one Cronbach alpha are reported and the author(s) refers to more than one central variable, we calculate the mean. If they only report ranges, we take the mean of the minimum and the	

Variable name in dataset	Variable	Operationalization	Example
		maximum. If the alphas of the overall scale and subscales (e.g., in the case of source credibility) are reported, we only use the alpha for the overall scale. If only two items are used, we report the correlation coefficient if the latter was provided (e.g., $r=0.74$).	
<i>reli_iic</i>	Inter-item correlation	Codes the inter-item correlation or (.)=not reported	
<i>comment_qual</i>	Comment on quality	Reports coders' reflections on the quality of the measure and focuses on whether the items suit the construct under investigation.	

Note: A description/example is only provided if the variable name is not self-explanatory. Not all coded variables are analyzed in the paper.

Constructs

Table A3. List of the Original Names of Measured Constructs (without duplications)

ad c.*	newscaster c.
advertiser c.	newspaper advertising c.
answer c.	newspaper and TV coverage
article c.	newspaper c.
assuror c.	online & offline media c.
author c.	online encyclopedic information c.
blog author c.	online health information c.
blog c.	online information c.
blog post c.	online news channel c.
book c.	online news content c.
brand c.	online news c.
cable news c.	online news sources c.
candidate's political c.	online newspaper c.
channel c.	online source c.
communicator c.	organizational c.
company denial c.	overall newscast c.
content c.	platform c.
corporate blog c.	political candidate c.
c. of company	political candidate source c.
CSR report c.	politicians c.
customer review c.	PR practitioners c.
domain c.	press/news aggregator c.
domestic television c.	product advice c.
e-WOM channel c.	program c.
expert ratings c.	publisher c.
general and political news c.	relative media c.
general c. of political candidate	reporter c.
group c.	review c.
health information c.	reviewer c.
health statements c.	scholarly information c. on the web
hypothetical article c.	scientist c.
information c.	search result c.
information c. on microblog sites	site c.
information c. on website	social media c.
information source c.	social media c./other inform. source
information source medium c.	source c.
institutional gatekeeper c.	source c. of a government agency
instructor c.	source c. of twitter risk messages
interloper candidate c.	spokesperson c.
international television c.	sponsor c.
internet c.	sportscaster source c.
internet journalists c.	statement c.
journalist c.	story c.
LinkedIn profile c.	structural c.
location information c.	support group c.

Table A3 continued

media advertising c.	testimonial c.
media channel c.	trust in newspapers and television
media c.	TV news and net news c.
message c.	TV news c.
message-relevant issues c.	TV news industry c.
microblog information c.	tweet c.
news article c.	user rating c.
news c.	weblog c.
news media c.	webpage source c.
news organization c.	website content c.
news producer c.	website c.
news program c.	website structural c.
news report c.	Wikipedia article c.
news story c.	

Note: *c.=credibility

Figure A1. Relevance of individual and collective source credibility over time

Figure A2. Relevance of different communication contexts over time

Measurement items

Table A4. List of the Original Names of the Items Used for Measurement

accurate	coherent
acceptable	colorful
active	competent
acts on behalf of	complete/provides complete information
aggressive	comprehensive
agreeable	concerned (about me)
(readers pay) attention to content	concern for readers/society etc.
attractive	concise
authentic	confident
author is affiliated with prestigious institution	considers xy's interests
authoritative	(presence of) contact information
available	contains credential of author
balanced	contains picture of author
believable/believable information	content is consistent with what I believe
beautiful	contextual
bold	convenient
bright	convincing
caring (about me)	cool
caring (about people/society)	correct/provides correct information
charming	company's intentions correspond with text
classy	coverage
clean	credible
clear	creative

Table A4 continued

critical	kind
current	knowledgeable
delivering a diversity of opinions	(document has a) nice layout
dependable	leading/being a leader in one's area
descriptive	likeable
detailed	xy liked the story
diplomatic	likelihood to read something
direct	likelihood to use something
dynamic	(document contains) links that do not work
efficient	live
elegant	(document is) long
emphasis	meaningful
empathic	meek
endorsing (third party endorsement)	xy is motivated by money
entertaining	motivation
ethical	moral
even-handed	(document has) multiple authorship
evidence-based	neutral
experienced	newsworthy
expert	nice
factual	non-sensational
fair	not misleading
favorable	not opinionated
fresh	not seeking commercial profit
friendly	not self-centered
genuine	objective
good/good job/good spokesperson	open-minded
good natured	organized
has a hidden agenda	others should believe
held the respondent's attention	partial
(is of) high quality	partisan
honorable	personal
honest (campaign/intentions)	persuasive
immediate	pleasant
important	powerful
includes major facts/tables and graphs	presence of privacy policy
includes references	prestigious
in depth	professional
influential	protects the public interest
informative/good source of info	provides information needed
informed	prudent
integrity	published
intelligent	qualified
interactive	reads articles by authors printed in journals
has xy's interests at heart	real
interesting	reasonable
intimate	recognized
involving	reflects things as they are
just	relevant

Table A4 continued

reliable	true/makes truthful claims
renowned	trustworthy
representative	(document has) typos
reputable	unbiased
respects people's privacy	understandable
responsible	understanding
safe	unselfish
sensitive	up to date
separates facts/opinions	useful
serious	valuable
sexy	verifiable
sincere	virtuous
site organization	(contains meter for) visit numbers
skilled/skills necessary	visual
slanted	vivid
sociable	warm
soft	watches out for xy's interests
sophisticated	website architecture
straight	(issues are) well addressed
substantive	(posted in a) well respected website
successful	well written/written by prof. journalists
(products of) superior quality	willingly lie
tells the whole story	willingness to recommend
thoroughly (researched)	willingness to work for sponsor
timely	won't misuse personal information
tone	working for the public good
trained (reporters)	

Table A5. Frequency of Item Use by Construct

Item	N (total)	source (n=125)			media (n=60)	message (n=74)
		individual	collective	both		
<i>accurate</i>	97	5	18	4	27	43
<i>active</i>	6	3	1	0	2	0
<i>aggressive</i>	4	0	0	1	3	0
<i>attractive</i>	7	4	2	1	0	0
<i>authentic</i>	3	0	0	0	0	3
<i>authoritative</i>	4	1	1	1	1	0
<i>balanced</i>	13	0	2	1	2	8
<i>believable (information)</i>	78	8	11	4	24	31
<i>bold</i>	5	1	0	1	3	0
<i>bright</i>	13	10	1	2	0	0
<i>caring (about me)</i>	13	9	1	3	0	0
<i>caring (about people)</i>	3	2	0	0	1	0
<i>classy</i>	3	2	1	0	0	0
<i>clear</i>	4	0	0	0	1	3
<i>competent</i>	25	18	4	2	1	0
<i>complete</i>	21	1	1	2	5	12
<i>comprehensive</i>	7	1	1	1	3	1
<i>concerned (about me)</i>	11	8	1	2	0	0
<i>concern for readers etc.</i>	11	2	3	1	5	0
<i>convincing</i>	7	0	3	0	0	4
<i>credible</i>	71	17	11	3	17	23
<i>current</i>	5	0	4	0	0	1
<i>dependable</i>	5	3	0	0	1	1
<i>ethical</i>	15	11	1	3	0	0
<i>experienced</i>	16	9	5	0	2	0
<i>expert</i>	49	24	11	7	3	4
<i>factual</i>	10	0	3	0	2	5
<i>fair</i>	54	6	14	1	14	19
<i>friendly</i>	5	1	3	1	0	0
<i>genuine</i>	14	10	1	2	0	1
<i>good</i>	9	2	5	1	0	1
<i>honorable</i>	13	10	1	2	0	0
<i>honest</i>	44	22	12	7	3	0
<i>includes major facts etc.</i>	3	0	0	0	1	2
<i>in depth</i>	11	0	1	1	8	1
<i>informative</i>	8	0	0	1	2	5
<i>informed</i>	22	14	4	4	0	0
<i>integrity</i>	3	3	0	0	0	0
<i>intelligent</i>	21	13	4	4	0	0
<i>has xy's interests at heart</i>	12	8	1	3	0	0
<i>interesting</i>	6	1	0	1	0	4
<i>intimate</i>	3	0	0	0	3	0
<i>involving</i>	3	1	0	1	1	0
<i>just</i>	4	2	0	0	2	0
<i>kind</i>	3	3	0	0	0	0
<i>knowledgeable</i>	8	6	1	1	0	0
<i>moral</i>	15	10	3	2	0	0

Item	N (total)	source (n=125)			media	message
		individual	collective	both	(n=60)	(n=74)
<i>newsworthy</i>	3	0	0	0	0	3
<i>nice</i>	4	2	1	1	0	0
<i>not self-centered</i>	12	9	0	2	1	0
<i>objective</i>	7	0	2	0	2	3
<i>open-minded</i>	3	2	0	0	1	0
<i>personal</i>	4	0	0	0	4	0
<i>pleasant</i>	8	3	3	2	0	0
<i>professional</i>	5	3	0	1	1	0
<i>qualified</i>	18	11	6	1	0	0
<i>reliable</i>	27	8	6	2	4	7
<i>reputable</i>	4	3	0	0	0	1
<i>respects people's privacy</i>	3	0	1	0	2	0
<i>safe</i>	4	3	0	1	0	0
<i>sensitive</i>	12	9	1	2	0	0
<i>separates facts/opinions</i>	3	0	2	0	1	0
<i>sincere</i>	12	8	4	0	0	0
<i>skilled/skills necessary</i>	8	7	1	0	0	0
<i>tells the whole story</i>	26	2	9	1	3	11
<i>trained (reporters)</i>	21	12	5	2	2	0
<i>true/makes truthful claims</i>	11	1	1	2	1	6
<i>trustworthy</i>	123	33	30	11	18	31
<i>unbiased</i>	50	6	8	5	11	20
<i>understanding</i>	7	4	0	1	1	1
<i>unselfish</i>	5	1	3	1	0	0
<i>valuable</i>	6	0	3	2	0	1
<i>virtuous</i>	3	1	1	1	0	0
<i>watches out for xy's interest</i>	3	0	2	0	1	0
<i>well written</i>	3	1	0	0	0	2
<i>other items (n=123)*</i>	164	40	27	13	34	50

Note: *Items include all items that were only used once or twice

Table A6. Frequency of Item Use by Communication Context

Item	online (n=147)	offline (n=70)	other/various (n=34)
<i>accurate</i>	56	27	13
<i>active</i>	1	5	0
<i>aggressive</i>	1	3	0
<i>attractive</i>	5	2	0
<i>authentic</i>	3	0	0
<i>authoritative</i>	3	0	1
<i>balanced</i>	10	2	1
<i>believable (information)</i>	47	15	15
<i>bold</i>	1	4	0
<i>bright</i>	13	0	0
<i>caring (about me)</i>	12	1	0
<i>caring (about people)</i>	2	1	0
<i>classy</i>	3	0	0
<i>clear</i>	1	1	1
<i>competent</i>	20	4	1
<i>complete</i>	15	3	3
<i>comprehensive</i>	6	0	1
<i>concerned (about me)</i>	11	0	0
<i>concern for readers etc.</i>	3	6	2
<i>convincing</i>	6	1	0
<i>credible</i>	38	20	9
<i>current</i>	3	2	0
<i>dependable</i>	3	2	0
<i>ethical</i>	14	0	0
<i>experienced</i>	9	5	0
<i>expert</i>	35	6	3
<i>factual</i>	4	3	2
<i>fair</i>	28	18	7
<i>friendly</i>	4	1	0
<i>genuine</i>	13	0	0
<i>good</i>	6	3	0
<i>honorable</i>	13	0	0
<i>honest</i>	30	13	0
<i>includes major facts etc.</i>	3	0	0
<i>in depth</i>	7	0	4
<i>informative</i>	6	1	1
<i>informed</i>	18	3	0
<i>integrity</i>	2	1	0
<i>intelligent</i>	18	2	0
<i>has xy's interests at heart</i>	12	0	0
<i>interesting</i>	6	0	0
<i>intimate</i>	0	3	0
<i>involving</i>	1	2	0
<i>just</i>	0	4	0
<i>kind</i>	0	3	0
<i>knowledgeable</i>	6	1	1
<i>moral</i>	15	0	0
<i>newsworthy</i>	1	2	0

Item	online (n=147)	offline (n=70)	other/various (n=34)
<i>nice</i>	2	2	0
<i>not self-centered</i>	11	1	0
<i>objective</i>	3	2	2
<i>open-minded</i>	1	1	0
<i>personal</i>	0	4	0
<i>pleasant</i>	5	3	0
<i>professional</i>	2	2	1
<i>qualified</i>	12	5	0
<i>reliable</i>	21	5	1
<i>reputable</i>	3	1	0
<i>respects people's privacy</i>	0	1	2
<i>safe</i>	1	3	0
<i>sensitive</i>	12	0	0
<i>separates facts/opinions</i>	1	1	1
<i>sincere</i>	7	5	0
<i>skilled/skills necessary</i>	5	2	0
<i>tells the whole story</i>	9	15	2
<i>trained (reporters)</i>	16	3	1
<i>true/makes truthful claims</i>	5	4	1
<i>trustworthy</i>	78	34	9
<i>unbiased</i>	25	17	7
<i>understanding</i>	5	0	1
<i>unselfish</i>	4	0	0
<i>valuable</i>	6	0	0
<i>virtuous</i>	2	1	0
<i>watches out for xy's interests</i>	1	1	1
<i>well written</i>	2	1	0
<i>other items (n=123)*</i>	91	57	8

Note: *Items include all items that were used only once or twice. The items competent, expert, informed, intelligent and trained are significantly (at least on the 10%-level) more frequent in online than in offline scales. The item “tells the whole story” is significantly more common in the offline than in the online context (p=0.001).

Details on cluster analysis

Table A7. List of Regrouped Items

<i>New items</i>	<i>Regrouped items</i>
accurate	accurate, correct, true, real, factual information
attractive	attractive, beautiful, sexy
authentic (II)	authentic, genuine
believable (II)	believable, believable information, others should believe something
caring	caring about me, about society, working for the public good, acts on behalf of its community
classy	classy, elegant
clear	clear, coherent, efficient, organized, site organization, understandable, well written
complete	complete, comprehensive, coverage, detailed, in depth, includes major facts, involving, reflects information as it is, provides information needed, tells the whole story, thoroughly, not partial, issues well addressed
concern	concern for the individual, the community, society, consider the reader's interests, has my interests at heart, watches out for people's interests
confident	confident, cool
convenient (II)	available, convenient, timely
current	current, up-to-date, fresh, immediate
ethical	moral, ethical, honorable, virtuous, good
evidence	contains credentials, third party endorsement, evidence-based, includes references, verifiable
honest	honest, runs an honest campaign, has honest intentions, direct, integrity, sincere, straight
informed	informed, knowledgeable
intelligent	intelligent, bright, reasonable
interesting (II)	interesting, newsworthy
likelihood to do something	likelihood, willingness to read xx, use xx, recommend xx, to work for xx
objective (II)	balanced, unbiased, delivering a diversity of opinions, even-handed, fair, just, not opinionated, neutral, objective, separates facts and opinions, slanted, open-minded
personal	personal, intimate
persuasive (II)	convincing, effective, persuasive
pleasant (II)	agreeable, charming, entertaining, likeable, nice, pleasant
powerful (II)	active, affiliated with a prestigious institution, dynamic, important, influential, leading, powerful, prestigious, renowned, reputable, well-respected, recognized
privacy	item invades privacy, respects people's privacy, won't misuse personal info
profit	not seeking commercial profit, motivated by money
qualified	trained, skilled, sophisticated, qualified, professional, expert, experienced, competent
quality	(products) are of superior, high quality

<i>New items</i>	<i>Regrouped items</i>
relevant (II)	meaningful, relevant
reliable (II)	reliable, dependable, authoritative, responsible
trustworthy (II)	trustworthy information/source, safe
understanding	diplomatic, kind, sensitive, understanding, empathetic, good natured
unselfish	unselfish, not self-centered
useful (II)	good source of information, informative, useful, valuable
vivid (II)	vivid, descriptive, colorful
warm	warm, sociable, friendly, soft

Note: Items marked with (II) are items for which items that could refer to either source/media or message were also regrouped. These were used for a final cluster analysis (see Figure A5 and tables A13 to A16 in this document).

Figure A3. Dendrogram for the cluster analysis with the regrouped items (synonyms)

Table A8. Frequency of Item Use by Cluster (regrouped items)

Item	N (total)	Cluster (regrouped items)		
		1 (N=156)	2 (N=17)	3 (N=68)
<i>accurate*</i>	109	43	0	66
<i>active</i>	6	5	0	1
<i>aggressive</i>	4	1	0	3
<i>attractive*</i>	7	4	2	1
<i>authentic</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>authoritative</i>	4	3	0	1
<i>balanced</i>	13	2	0	11
<i>believable</i>	78	45	0	33
<i>bold</i>	5	2	0	3
<i>caring*</i>	19	9	10	0
<i>classy*</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>clear*</i>	13	6	2	5
<i>complete*</i>	75	11	0	64
<i>concern*</i>	23	9	11	3
<i>confident*</i>	4	2	0	2
<i>convincing</i>	7	7	0	0
<i>credible</i>	71	66	2	3
<i>current*</i>	7	4	0	3
<i>dependable</i>	5	5	0	0
<i>ethical*</i>	26	11	15	0
<i>evidence*</i>	6	4	0	2
<i>fair</i>	54	11	0	43
<i>genuine</i>	14	3	11	0
<i>honest*</i>	50	29	17	4
<i>informative</i>	8	4	0	4
<i>informed*</i>	30	13	17	0
<i>intelligent*</i>	23	6	17	0
<i>interesting</i>	6	4	0	2
<i>just</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>likelihood to do something*</i>	4	3	0	1
<i>newsworthy</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>nice</i>	4	0	4	0
<i>objective</i>	7	3	0	4
<i>open-minded</i>	3	2	0	1
<i>personal*</i>	4	2	0	2
<i>pleasant</i>	8	1	6	1
<i>privacy*</i>	4	2	0	2
<i>qualified*</i>	65	41	17	7
<i>quality*</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>reliable</i>	27	15	6	6
<i>reputable</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>safe</i>	4	1	2	1
<i>separates facts and opinions</i>	3	0	0	3
<i>trustworthy</i>	123	57	15	51
<i>unbiased</i>	50	7	0	43
<i>understanding*</i>	19	5	13	1

Item	N (total)	Cluster (regrouped items)		
		1 (N=156)	2 (N=17)	3 (N=68)
<i>unselfish*</i>	17	2	14	1
<i>valuable</i>	6	1	4	1
<i>warm*</i>	9	1	6	2
<i>other items (n=74)**</i>	94	74	2	18

Note: *These items were regrouped based on their meaning (synonyms);

**Items that include all items only used once or twice

Additional cluster analysis I

Figure A4. Dendrogram for the cluster analysis with the original items

Table A9. Cluster Attribution by Construct (original items, row percent)

	source N (%)	media N (%)	message N (%)	Total
<i>Cluster 1</i>	81 (49.1)	40 (24.2)	44 (26.7)	165 (100.0)
<i>Cluster 2</i>	13 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	13 (100.0)
<i>Cluster 3</i>	19 (30.2)	19 (30.2)	25 (39.7)	63 (100.0)

Table A10. Cluster Attribution by Construct (original items, column percent)

	source N (%)	media N (%)	message N (%)
<i>Cluster 1</i>	81 (71.7)	40 (67.8)	44 (63.8)
<i>Cluster 2</i>	13 (11.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
<i>Cluster 3</i>	19 (16.8)	19 (32.2)	25 (36.2)
Total	113 (100.0)	59 (100.0)	69 (100.0)

Table A11. Cluster Attribution by Context (original items, row percent)

	online N (%)	offline N (%)	other/various N (%)	Total
<i>Cluster 1</i>	89 (56.7)	43 (27.4)	25 (15.9)	157 (100.0)
<i>Cluster 2</i>	13 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	13 (100.0)
<i>Cluster 3</i>	35 (55.6)	19 (30.2)	9 (14.3)	63 (100.0)

Table A12. Frequency of Item Use by Cluster (original items)

Item	N (total)	Cluster (original items)		
		1 (N=165)	2 (N=13)	3 (N=63)
<i>accurate</i>	97	35	0	62
<i>active</i>	6	6	0	0
<i>aggressive</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>attractive</i>	7	7	0	0
<i>authentic</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>authoritative</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>balanced</i>	13	2	0	11
<i>believable (information)</i>	78	51	0	27
<i>bold</i>	5	5	0	0
<i>bright</i>	13	0	13	0
<i>caring (about me)</i>	13	3	10	0
<i>caring (about people)</i>	3	2	0	1
<i>classy</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>clear</i>	4	2	0	2
<i>competent</i>	25	12	13	0
<i>complete</i>	21	6	0	15
<i>comprehensive</i>	7	2	0	5
<i>concerned (about me)</i>	11	0	11	0
<i>concern for readers etc.</i>	11	8	0	3
<i>convincing</i>	7	7	0	0
<i>credible</i>	71	68	0	3
<i>current</i>	5	3	0	2
<i>dependable</i>	5	5	0	0
<i>ethical</i>	15	2	13	0
<i>experienced</i>	16	16	0	0
<i>expert</i>	49	33	13	3
<i>factual</i>	10	5	0	5
<i>fair</i>	54	6	0	48
<i>friendly</i>	5	5	0	0
<i>genuine</i>	14	1	13	0
<i>good</i>	9	9	0	0
<i>honorable</i>	13	0	13	0
<i>honest</i>	44	29	13	2
<i>includes major facts etc.</i>	3	1	0	2
<i>in depth</i>	11	1	0	10
<i>informative</i>	8	4	0	4
<i>informed</i>	22	9	13	0
<i>integrity</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>intelligent</i>	21	9	12	0
<i>has xy's interests at heart</i>	12	1	11	0
<i>interesting</i>	6	5	0	1
<i>intimate</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>involving</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>just</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>kind</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>knowledgeable</i>	8	8	0	0
<i>moral</i>	15	2	13	0

Item	N (total)	Cluster (original items)		
		1 (N=165)	2 (N=13)	3 (N=63)
<i>newsworthy</i>	3	0	0	3
<i>nice</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>not self-centered</i>	12	1	10	1
<i>objective</i>	7	2	0	5
<i>open-minded</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>personal</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>pleasant</i>	8	8	0	0
<i>professional</i>	5	5	0	0
<i>qualified</i>	18	18	0	0
<i>reliable</i>	27	22	0	5
<i>reputable</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>respects people's privacy</i>	3	1	0	2
<i>safe</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>sensitive</i>	12	1	11	0
<i>separates facts/opinions</i>	3	0	0	3
<i>sincere</i>	12	12	0	0
<i>skilled/skills necessary</i>	8	8	0	0
<i>tells the whole story</i>	26	3	0	23
<i>trained (reporters)</i>	21	5	13	3
<i>true/makes truthful claims</i>	11	11	0	0
<i>trustworthy</i>	123	64	13	46
<i>unbiased</i>	50	8	0	42
<i>understanding</i>	7	2	5	0
<i>unselfish</i>	5	5	0	0
<i>valuable</i>	6	6	0	0
<i>virtuous</i>	3	3	0	0
<i>watches out for xy's interests</i>	3	0	0	3
<i>well written</i>	3	0	0	3
<i>other items (n=123)*</i>	164	140	0	24

Note: *Items that include all items only used once or twice

Additional cluster analysis II

Figure A5. Dendrogram for the cluster analysis with the regrouped items (II)

Table A13. Cluster attribution by construct (regrouped items II, row percent)

	source N (%)	media N (%)	message N (%)	Total
Cluster 1	43 (36.8)	31 (26.5)	43 (36.8)	117 (100.0)
Cluster 2	42 (95.5)	1 (2.3)	1 (2.3)	44 (100.0)
Cluster 3	28 (35.0)	27 (33.8)	25 (31.3)	80 (100.0)

Table A14. Cluster attribution by construct (regrouped items II, column percent)

	source N (%)	media N (%)	message N (%)
Cluster 1	43 (38.1)	31 (52.5)	43 (62.3)
Cluster 2	42 (37.2)	1 (1.7)	1 (1.5)
Cluster 3	28 (24.8)	27 (45.8)	25 (36.2)
Total	113 (100.0)	59 (100.0)	69 (100.0)

Table A15. Cluster attribution by context (regrouped items II, row percent)

	online N (%)	offline N (%)	other/various N (%)	Total
Cluster 1	62 (56.4)	29 (26.4)	19 (17.3)	110 (100.0)
Cluster 2	33 (76.7)	8 (18.6)	2 (4.7)	43 (100.0)
Cluster 3	42 (52.5)	25 (31.3)	13 (16.3)	80 (100.0)

Table A16. Frequency of item use by cluster (regrouped items II)

Item	N (total)	Cluster (regrouped items II)		
		1 (N=110)	2 (N=43)	3 (N=80)
accurate*	109	39	0	70
aggressive	4	0	0	4
attractive*	7	0	5	2
authentic*	17	4	13	0
believable*	78	48	2	28
bold	5	0	0	5
caring*	19	2	13	4
classy*	3	0	3	0
clear*	13	4	2	7
complete*	75	6	1	68
concern*	23	4	12	7
confident*	4	2	0	2
convenient*	3	0	0	3
credible	71	53	9	9
current*	7	0	0	7
ethical*	26	2	19	5
evidence*	6	3	1	2
honest*	50	4	37	9
informed*	30	2	27	1
intelligent*	23	0	22	1
interesting*	9	6	1	2
likelihood to do sth.*	4	2	2	0
objective*	84	10	1	73
personal*	4	0	0	4
persuasive*	9	6	1	2
pleasant*	11	0	7	4
powerful*	17	5	6	6
privacy*	4	1	0	3
qualified*	65	15	34	16
quality*	3	2	1	0
reliable*	32	10	11	11
trustworthy*	124	23	41	60
understanding*	19	2	15	2
unselfish*	17	0	16	1
useful*	13	4	4	5
vivid*	3	0	0	3
warm*	9	0	6	3
other items (n=42)**	56	25	13	18

Note: *These items were regrouped based on their meaning (synonyms).

**Items that include all items only used once or twice

References

- Appelman, A., & Sundar, S. S. (2016). Measuring message credibility. Construction and validation of an exclusive scale. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 93(1), 59–79.
- Carifio, J., & Perla, R. J. (2007). Ten common misunderstandings, misconceptions, persistent myths and urban legends about Likert scales and Likert response formats and their antidotes. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(3), 106–116. <https://doi.org/10.3844/jssp.2007.106.116>
- Gaziano, C., & McGrath, K. (1986). Measuring the concept of credibility. *Journalism Quarterly*, 63(3), 451–462. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769908606300301>
- Johnson, T. J., Kaye, B. K., Bichard, S. L., & Wong, W. J. (2007). Every blog has its day: Politically-interested internet users' perceptions of blog credibility. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 100–122. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00388.x>
- Liu, Z., & Huang, X. (2005). Evaluating the credibility of scholarly information on the web: A cross cultural study. *International Information & Library Review*, 37(2), 99–106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10572317.2005.10762670>
- Pjesivac, I., & Rui, R. (2014). Anonymous sources hurt credibility of news stories across cultures: A comparative experiment in America and China. *International Communication Gazette*, 76(8), 641–660. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748048514548534>
- Tewksbury, D., Jensen, J., & Coe, K. (2011). Video news releases and the public: The impact of source labeling on the perceived credibility of television news. *Journal of Communication*, 61(2), 328–348. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2011.01542.x>